

LOOKING INTO BANK PREFERENCES IN SME'S FINANCING DECISIONS, A CASE FROM DKI JAKARTA, INDONESIA

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Abstract

Purpose – The authors examine the willingness of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to do business with banks. Since the object is known as one of SME's Centre located in Jakarta, Indonesia, a conducive environment was given regarding access to the financing sources like banking by the government authority, and most of the entrepreneurs in the research object were found to be literate, and there is a need for a systematic recording of their transactions. These records will help to open access to financial institutions.

Design/methodology/approach – We survey the specificity of their financing decision in using banking as their source of funds. We employ a logit model and descriptive statistics in interpreting the survey. **Findings** – SMEs' bank choices are more strongly associated with financial records accuracy, rather than accommodative banking access availability. The motivation for using bank financing as their source of funds is likely driven by their self-confidence in running their business, reflected by the accuracy of their financial records.

Research limitations/implications – We could have drawn a more detailed picture of the bank selection that offered SME financing programs. Especially by classifying the source of funds programs with Shariah and conventional financing. **Practical implications** – The study shows that the issue of religiosity arises in choosing sources of funds as an alternative source of funds. The bankable issue of financial records requirement is not regarded as a barrier, nor is the easiness in getting the funds for the SMEs in choosing sources of financing from banks. Another financial literacy approach from financial institutions such as banks needs to explore and socialize to have a good relationship in bank financing products for the SME industry. **Originality/value** – By addressing the engagement of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Indonesia that could help sustain the country's economic growth, the topic of bank selection for their financing sources of funds by SMEs has not been thoroughly investigated. We address this gap by analyzing two types of potential drivers of bank selection from SMEs' points of view: financial records accuracy and accommodative banking access availability.

Keywords: SMEs, Financial Records, Banking Access, Bank Selection, Financing Decision

1. INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) continue to expand, not with global economic instabilities and a more competitive marketplace. The recognition of SMEs as a key driver of economic growth in Indonesia is well recognized by the Indonesian government. Indonesia's SME documented an impressive credit averaging 684,494.247 billion IDR from January 2011 to May 2019 (Global Database's Indonesia: Small and Medium Enterprises: Credit, accessed from <https://www.ceicdata.com/en/in>). The growth reflects the entrepreneurial spirit and is motivated by some reasons. E.g. flexibility, independence, or to earn more money (Orlando and Pollack, 2000). The huge power and potential within SMEs were undoubtedly counted and supported by featuring in the Mid Term Development Program 2015-2019 and became one of the top priorities. Therefore, actions and reforms were taken seriously to support and strengthen SME productivity, innovation activity, and global participation in the global market (OECD, 2018). Academic evidence from developed countries is, at best, mixed about

the role of government assistance programs targeting the SME sector (Harrison and Mason, 2000).

As a result, many programs and policies aim to make reforms in some critical aspect that are suspected as problems for SMEs. Some improvements set out to ease SMEs' business activities, such as the procurement process of raw materials and marketing and the most prominent issue in financial access known as People's Business Credit in 2007 (Tambunan, 2018). The most significant policy that became a framework for SMEs is issuing the Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprise (MSME) Law Number 20/ 2008. It aims to increase the role and capabilities of MSMEs on a regional and international scale by increasing Indonesia's economic growth through MSMEs. Micro and small enterprises dominate the proportion of MSEs in Indonesia, and based on Law No. 20/ 2008, the criteria for a firm to be classified as a 'small enterprise' are having net assets, excluding land and buildings, of between 50 million IDR and 500 million IDR, or having annual sales of between 300 million IDR and 2.5 billion IDR since the micro and medium-sized enterprises contribute 58% to 61% to Indonesia's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and show the feature of Indonesian SMEs (Tambunan, 2019).

The characteristics of SMEs in Indonesia are closely related to common problems like informational problems and lack of access to financial services. Informational problems lead to how the SMEs record their transactions and manages their business in a systematic order of informal reports. The study in Kenya showed that many SME record their sales using a double-entry system, and it positively increased SMEs' profitability (Chelimo and Sophia, 2014). Most studies point out that even though SMEs have a big contribution to economic growth but have not successfully run the business, pieces of literature documented that, most likely due to the lack of transaction records or bookkeeping (Chepkemoi, 2013). Micro and small-size features of SMEs contribute to the traditional management and simple recording that is far from the demanded standards of formal organizations.

SMEs in Indonesia, many MSME actors only have education as high school, junior high school, and even elementary school graduates, which cause a lack of human resources capable of managing finances properly, so the implementation of bookkeeping is difficult and complicated for MSMEs (Rudiantoro & Siregar, 2012). The mindset also makes the situation worse, MSME managers consider financial reports not important (Putra and Kurniawati, 2012). Another empirical investigation supports the study, where it is found that only 22.5% of MSME actors have financial reports, and 87.8% prepare financial reports inappropriately in North Sumatera, it had documented that the bookkeeping system of MSMEs has been generally very simple and tends to ignore standard (standard) financial administration principles (Harahap and Bisnis, 2014).

While the financial accessibility of SMEs became another top issue, ERIA's SME researcher documented that access to financial services is the most prominent factor for SMEs in achieving competitiveness (Thanh *et al.*, 2010). Many countries that rely on MSMEs as their engine for GDP (Gross Domestic Product) are struggling with many constraints, especially lack of access to financing services, difficulties in marketing, and limited access to advanced technologies and skilled workers ((Orlando and Pollack, 2000); (Yuhua, 2013); (Thanh *et al.*,

2010); (Tambunan, 2018); (Thapa, 2016)). The micro and small size of Indonesian SMEs will cause a lack of collateral/income, high-risk debtor classification, and automatically will exclude them from the list of financing customer banking institutions. This condition not only happened in Indonesia, Baata (2008) found that Mongolia's SMEs' prominent barrier in detail is the banking standards requirements which included high-interest rates, collateral, very little option on long-term loans, and inadequate business plan.

Contra to the majority condition, there were shreds of evidence that some SMEs do have access and categorized bankable as they meet the financing requirements from banks and other microfinance institutions. Interestingly, they choose not to use the financing option rather rely on internal sources of funds such as retained earnings, personal savings, or family support. Based on empirical data from 3 provinces of manufacturing SMEs in Indonesia (West Java, Central Java, and East Java) found that 56% of respondents with access to financial services decided not to take the opportunity and a significant portion consist almost half of respondents do not have access to financial services (Machmud & Huda, 2011). Therefore, it is essential to understand SME financing decisions (choice whether to use financial services or not) considering the national mission in bringing MSME role and capabilities for economic growth, recent studies confirmed the important role of SMEs in many other emerging countries like Malaysia (Madanchian et al., 2015), Morocco (Hassan & Mohamed, 2015), and South Africa (Kongolo, 2010).

In this study, we examine the behavior of micro and small SMEs in their financing decision whether they willing to take financial services offered by banks. Our research object focused on SMEs supported by the local government (DKI Jakarta) to ensure a conducive environment for their management and accessibility to financial services. More specifically, the study investigates the accuracy of financial record transactions and the perception of the financial access accommodativeness for selecting financial banking services. Furthermore, the study analyzes the adequate characteristics of bankable SMEs: the requirements of the financial standards and the accommodative financial access. The object is one of the SME's centers in Pulogadung, East Jakarta, Indonesia. Small Industrial Village (PIK or short for Perkampungan Industri Kecil) with 691 members of SMEs and occupy 1,261 units of business facilities. It is a business area for creative industries integrated with easy access based on Transit Oriented Development (TOD).

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Financial institutions' perspectives had a common belief that SMEs are not the ideal borrower. Reasoning the statements will come to picture of traditional management and limited financial capacity that easily found in most of SMEs especially in developing countries or emerging market ((Beck et al., 2008);(Naidu & Chand, 2012); (Meslier et al., 2020). Limited access to financial services which is mostly caused by opacity and informational asymmetry (Berger & Udell, 2005) demonstrate a credit rationing where hidden information will take a part (Stiglitz & Weiss, 1981). Moreover, SME firms in emerging markets had poor financial disclosure ((Sami & Zhou, 2008) ;(Zhou, 2007);(Klonowski, 2007)). Consequently, the situation makes

the potential moral hazards increase in emerging markets ((Klonowski, 2007); (Tagoe et al., 2005)). Finally, SMEs will not be classified as investment-ready (Mason & Kwok, 2010); (Hughes, 2009); (Oakey, 2007); (R. T Harrison & Mason, 2004)).

Keeping in mind that Indonesian SMEs dominantly micro and small size enterprises with almost 100% (Tambunan, 2019). Moreover, these types of SMEs possess only limited collateral and most of their owner had the lack management skills (Mazzarol & Reboud, 2020). Therefore, assessing their creditworthiness standards will end with gathering significant soft information ((Stein, 2002); (Udell, 2008)). Less comprehensive financial reports are highly associated with soft or opaque information, where their transaction records do not adequately meet the accounting standards criteria. The presentation report of SMEs typically showed less formal than larger firms and consequently, it makes SMEs seen riskier. (Hasanah et al., 2019) found that SMEs in Bogor, Indonesia do have the ability to simple accounting transaction records with the “Single Entry” method. The method only one alternative that has been used until now and the scattered information about SMEs financial record transaction vary among MSMEs.

The opaque information is the reflection of information asymmetry, and it should be gathered in shaping the accuracy of financial record transactions for SMEs. Identifying the adequate characteristics of financial records for bankable SMEs which meet the requirements of financial access becomes an urgency. Since MSMEs had backup support from the government for strengthening Indonesia’s economic growth. Presidential Instruction Number 6/ 2007, the government introduced a credit scheme for micro and small enterprises People's Business Credit. The government-guaranteed loans are directed to MSMEs as well as cooperatives which are productive and feasible businesses. The scheme provides funds up to 500 million IDR through commercial banks assigned by the government and should be distributed to MSMEs (Wie, 2006). The financial access accommodativeness in the side of MSME’s point of view aimed to give an understanding of how the aid scheme being interpreted. Thus, analyzes the reaction from the perception towards the financial access accommodativeness for selecting the financial banking services. Furthermore, the study analyzes the accommodative financial access in helping MSMEs to act and benefit from the offered scheme by selecting the banking external sources of funds.

H1. SMEs that had a good perception of the accommodative financial access will tend to select the financial banking services as external sources of funds.

Narrowing the gap in information asymmetry becomes important for bank and MSMEs owner to have accurate information in building trust and decision-making usefulness. Therefore, the topic of bank selection for financing sources of MSMEs is by looking at the accuracy of their financial records, so we propose H2.

H2. SMEs that had the accuracy of financial record transactions are more likely to select the financial banking services as external sources of funds.

3. METHODOLOGY

In analyzing the specificity of MSMEs financing decision in using banking as their source of funds, by employing a logit model and descriptive statistics in interpreting the survey. By taking the observation area in the East Jakarta area and concentrating on the Small Industry Center (PIK) area in Pulogadung which has a population of 300 small traders registered in the PIK cooperative. The sampling method was carried out by a random sampling of 125 respondents from a total population of 300 SME entrepreneurs (Small and Medium Enterprises). Questionnaires were distributed for 5 days starting from 6 September to 10 September 2018.

Regression logit model

$$\text{Log} [(P/(1-P))] = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (\text{the accommodative financial access}) + \beta_2 (\text{the accuracy of financial record transactions}) + e$$

For the logit model, we regress a binary variable bank selection which takes the value 1 if the MSMEs select the financial banking services as external sources of funds, and 0 otherwise. This logit model to test hypothesis related to the probability of choosing the bank financing as their external sources of funds.

Test the validity of the variable **the accommodative financial access** or X1 because all items for access to capital (X1) have a total correlation score (r) greater than 0.25, so all items are said to be valid. Whereas for literacy variables on funding from financial institutions in the form of **the accuracy of financial record transactions** or X2, except for items for Q9 and Q14 which have a score of less than 0.25, all items have a total score greater than 0.25, the question item is for accuracy. Financial statement information (X2) is said to be valid.

Table 1: Variable Logit Model

No	Variables	Indicator	Code	Category	
1.	Selection of financial banking services as external sources of funds. (Y)		1	Selecting the financial banking services as external sources of funds.	
			0	Not selecting financial banking services as external sources of funds.	
2.	The accommodative financial access	Q1 Funding alternatives	1	Not Accommodating Simple / traditional conditions	
			2		
			3		Adequate conditions
			4		Very good condition
		Q2 Easy access	1	Not Accommodating Simple / traditional conditions	
			2		
			3		Adequate conditions
			4		Very good condition
		Q3 Banks requirements	1	Not Accommodating Simple / traditional conditions	
			2		
			3		Adequate conditions
			4		Very good condition
		Q4 Estimated Funding	1	Not Accommodating Simple / traditional conditions	
			2		
			3		Adequate conditions

		requirements	4	Very good condition
		Q5 Length of loan	1 2 3 4	Not Accommodating Simple / traditional conditions Adequate conditions Very good condition
		Q6 The institution best suited for the method	1 2 3 4	Not Accommodating Simple / traditional conditions Adequate conditions Very good condition
3.	The accuracy of financial record transactions	Q7- Q12 Aset	1 2 3 4	Inaccurate condition Low accuracy conditions Adequate conditions Highly accurate
		Q13-Q15 Equity	1 2 3 4	Inaccurate condition Low accuracy conditions Adequate conditions Highly accurate
		Q16-Q19 Revenue and Cost of good sold	1 2 3 4	Inaccurate condition Low accuracy conditions Adequate conditions Highly accurate
No	Variables	Indicator	Code	Category
		Q20-Q21 Expenses	1 2 3 4	Inaccurate condition Low accuracy conditions Adequate conditions Highly accurate
		Q22 Inventory	1 2 3 4	Inaccurate condition Low accuracy conditions Adequate conditions Highly accurate

Sources (draft questioners Researchers)

4. RESULTS

Hypothesis Testing

The model explained 37.9% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in the selection of the financial banking services as the external sources of funds and correctly classified 75.9% of cases. Refer to the regression slope 0,808 then $\text{Exp}(B) 2,720^{.8} = 2.23$. Therefore, there is a 2.23 times tendency that PIK Pulogadung MSMEs actors who have accurate financial records information will prefer to use external sources from banks. Or it could also be interpreted as the following sentence, that the PIK Pulogadung MSMEs actors prefer a source of funding from a bank for entrepreneurs who had the accurate financial records information compared to entrepreneurs who do not have the accurate financial information. SMEs' bank choices are more strongly associated with financial records accuracy, rather than accommodative banking access availability.

Table 2

Model Summary

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	102,556 ^a	,268	,379

a. Estimation terminated at iteration number 6 because parameter estimates changed by less than ,001.

Interestingly, by looking at table 3, and noted the Percentage Accuracy in Classification (PAC) which reflects the percentages of cases that can be correctly classified as Not selecting financial banking with 88,5%. The sensitivity, which is the percentage of cases that had the observed characteristic which was correctly predicted by the model 16%. Continue with the specificity, which is the percentage of cases that did not have the observed characteristic and were also correctly predicted as not having the observed characteristic 69%.

Table 3

Classification Table^a

Observed		Predicted		
		selection of financial naking services		
		Not selecting the financial banking services as external sources of funds	Selecting the financial banking services as external sources of funds.	Percentage Correct
Step 1	selection of financial naking services	69	9	88,5
	Not selecting the financial banking services as external sources of funds			
	Selecting the financial banking services as external sources of funds.	18	16	47,1
Overall Percentage				75,9

a. The cut value is ,500

Based on the significances coefficient result from testing the variables, we verify hypotheses H1 and H2 and present estimation results for logit models explaining the probability of Selecting the financial banking services as external sources of funds. The accuracy of financial record transactions instead of the accommodative financial. The outcomes suggest that SMEs tend to use external sources from banks if they have accurate financial records information (X2). The motivation in using bank financing as their source of funds likely driven by their self-confidence in running their business reflected by the accuracy of their financial records.

H1. SMEs that had a good perception of the accommodative financial access will tend to select the financial banking services as external sources of funds.

H2. SMEs that had the accuracy of financial record transactions are more likely to select the financial banking services as external sources of funds.

The relevant coefficients are statistically significant at 1% and 5% levels, respectively. Significance coefficients showed the accommodative financial access (X1) which is Q1, Q2, Q3, Q4, Q5, and Q6 found significance above 5%. While for the accuracy of financial record transactions (X2) documented coefficient significance 0.006 for Q8 and 0.02 for Q20. The significant coefficients generally support hypothesis H2, according to which SMEs considering their accuracy of financial record transactions in deciding to select the bank external financing. And there is no strong evidence in favor of hypothesis H1 as they indicate that SMEs not considering the accommodative financial access (X1) offered by the bank in selecting their preferences toward their selection of bank external financing.

Discussion

The logistic result should be read carefully, the hypothesis testing showed that there is a tendency that PIK Pulogadung MSMEs actors who have accurate financial records information will prefer to use external sources from banks. Explaining this condition that confirmed with significant coefficients from Q8 and Q 20,

Q8: Sales transactions are carried out

- Not recorded
- Just consignment
- Just cash
- Cash and credit

Table 4

The accuracy of financial record transactions

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Inaccurate condition	15	12,0	12,5	12,5
	Low accuracy conditios	12	9,6	10,0	22,5
	Adequate conditions	35	28,0	29,2	51,7
	Highly accurate	58	46,4	48,3	100,0
	Total	120	96,0	100,0	
Missing	System	5	4,0		
Total		125	100,0		

Based on question 8, it can be said that statistically, 46.4% of the recording conditions that occurred in PIK were recorded in either cash or credit recording conditions which were classified as high accuracy or very good recording conditions. In full, the recording conditions in the PIK environment show a conducive condition, this is indicated by the second-highest percentage of 28% which states that recording is only for cash transactions that fall into the classification of the accuracy of adequate financial statement information. This means that as many as 74.4% of entrepreneurs in PIK Pulogadung have recorded either the cash method approach or the accrual method approach (cash-cash recording). More than half of the population in the study sample had carried out adequate records.

Q 20: The costs that are often paid by MSMEs for MSME operation activities during production activities range from,

- Under IDR 100,000 / day
- IDR 100,000 - IDR 500,000 / day
- IDR 500,000 - IDR 1,000,000 / day
- Over IDR 1,000,000 / day

Table 5

The accuracy of financial record transactions

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Inaccurate condition	63	50,4	52,5	52,5
	Low accuracy conditios	38	30,4	31,7	84,2
	Adequate conditions	7	5,6	5,8	90,0
	Highly accurate	12	9,6	10,0	100,0
	Total	120	96,0	100,0	
Missing	System	5	4,0		
Total		125	100,0		

The cost expenditure pattern also reflects the condition of the high accuracy of financial statement information, which is shown by the costs that are often paid by MSMEs for very efficient operations in the range of below Rp 100,000 / day. A documented efficiency percentage of 50.4% followed by an adequate accuracy condition of 30.4% in the range of IDR 100,000-IDR 500,000. This means that 80.4% succeeded in making very effective expenditures. This efficiency condition is very good, meaning that half of the population of entrepreneurs in PIK who the research samples have both wholesale and retail types with a market share of 52.5% (discussion of descriptive statistical analysis).

Information on respondent data from open statements (Attachment to the recapitulation of PIK respondents' questions) concluded that the costs incurred during the activity were costs, including transportation, labor, cleanliness, food/consumption, security fees, electricity, and parking. The list of costs is the cost most frequently mentioned by respondents in open-ended questions. On average, each respondent shows that the costs incurred in each business range from 2-3 cost allocations.

However, in the reality, many respondents did not take advantage of access to financial institutions, namely half of the population in the study sample. Noted the Percentage Accuracy in Classification (PAC) in Table 3. Which reflects the percentages of cases that can be correctly classified as not selecting financial banking with 88, 5%. Another confirmed data showed by the proportion of selection of financial banking services in table 7. Which 69.2% choose not to select the financial banking services as their external sources of funds? Combining the two pieces of information implied that neither the firms who met the requirements records of banking criteria and who did not meet the criteria for not selecting banking financing as their

external funds. This confirmed Han et al (2009) who documented that riskier firms maybe do not dare to take the option as bank financing customers because they do not believe they can obtain it.

Table 6

selection of financial naking services

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not selecting the financial banking services as external sources of funds	83	66,4	69,2	69,2
	Selecting the financial banking services as external sources of funds.	37	29,6	30,8	100,0
	Total	120	96,0	100,0	
Missing	System	5	4,0		
Total		125	100,0		

Many respondents did not disclose their reasons, from some who expressed their opinion on this reluctance to focus on one reason, namely because of the problem of usury which is closely related to aspects of religious beliefs that prefer not to be involved even though using Islamic banking.

The insignificance of the X1 variable, namely the accommodativeness of access to capital in this study, is factually reflected in the respondent's data, which in general can be classified as less conducive in interpreting the existence of external sources of funding. This is seen from the distribution of the dominant frequency that occurs in each question (Q1 to Q6) regarding the conditions of access to capital that exist in the PIK environment. In general, the sources of funding that have been occurring in PIK have come from family and private funds (Q1). Relations with financial institutions are also dominated by actors who have not used the services of financial institutions as creditors (Q2). Regarding the mindset towards the ease of borrowing from banks, it is still dominated by thoughts of having difficulty obtaining financial institution funding (Q3). The range of funding needs is also in a relatively small category with a value of less than IDR 5,000,000 (Q4). The estimated timeframe for the length of funding is also 1-2 years (Q5). Finally, the respondents stated that the cooperative monopolized the profit-sharing system that was most suitable for them (Q6).

The role of active participation of MSME actors who take advantage of the accessibility of financial institutions was found because of the ease with which they can obtain such funding. The convenience in question can be found in several versions, including because they were originally customers of the bank's savings product, ease of requirements in the banking industry (this is due to government incentives for banking institutions), banking locations that are close to the reach and speed of the loan process. The data also shows a preference that appears to occur in conventional banks due to easier conditions for them, more competitive interest, and easy access to locations.

Another explanation for the phenomenon of reluctance to take advantage of access to funding from financial institutions can also be explained by the type of most Indonesians who generally dislike risk. Other sources of funding will create pressure and risk of asset transfer with relatively fast time specifications (due to installments). They prefer a brotherhood system that prioritizes funding that comes from family, which of course is relatively lacking in terms of regulations. The feeling of security because of not being in debt is a reason besides being a factor of religious belief which also emphasizes the virtue of not being in debt, especially to conventional banks. This explanation is one of the reasons that can be put forward as an explanation for the phenomenon that occurs.

Underlining the government concerns in helping MSMEs in improving their access to finance through a financing banking scheme, there is a growing sentiment among researchers that government assistance programs not necessary since the capital market for SMEs are adequate ((Cosh et al., 2009); (Oakey, 2007);). Others argue that there is no supported empirical research for such a government scheme in bringing growth and Prosperity for SMEs ((Bill et al., 2009);(Lambrecht & Pirnay, 2005), (Wie, 2006)). Based on the empirical result it suggests that the pecking order theory is best suited to the PIK Pulogadung MSMEs' context (Myers & Majluf, 1984). Therefore, there is a hierarchical preference for sources of financing. This approach suggests that PIK MSMEs enterprises in Pulogadung prefer internal to external financing.

The insignificance of access to capital (variable X1) is because most businesses are family businesses that are generally reluctant to accept outside funding. Based on the response to the indicators of capital accessibility, it was found that consciously they did not want to play a role as creditors in financial institutions actively. The preference for a brotherhood system that relies on family and the feeling of security for not being in debt, especially to conventional banks, confirmed the study that showed that SMEs avoid losing control and can be aligned with the pecking order theory explanation ((Ang, 1991);(Holmes & Kent, 1991)).

5. CONCLUSION

Statistically, the data shows the potential and adequate accessibility of the PIK Pulogadung MSMEs by gathering an indicator of the accurate financial records information in the area. As many as 74.4% of entrepreneurs in PIK Pulogadung have recorded either using the cash method approach or the accrual method approach (cash-cash recording). More than half of the population in the study sample had carried out adequate records. Conclusively, the condition suggests that MSMEs with a good financial record featured with more than half of respondents qualified to be literate in recording their transaction and had the bank financing preferences.

The cost expenditure pattern also reflects the condition of the high accuracy of financial statement information, indicates low expenditure and the meaning is very good for efficiency considering that half of the population of entrepreneurs in PIK who the research sample were had both wholesale and retail types with a market share of 52.5%.

The model explained 37.9% with a 2.23 times tendency that PIK Pulogadung MSMEs actors who have accurate financial records information will prefer to use external sources from banks. SMEs' bank choices are more strongly associated with financial records accuracy, rather than accommodative banking access availability.

The study shows that the issue of religiosity arises in choosing sources of funds as an alternative source of funds. The bankable issue about financial records requirement is not regarded as a barrier neither is the easiness in getting the funds for the SME's in choosing sources of financing from banks. Another approach of financial literacy from financial institutions such as banks need to explore and get it to socialize to have a good relation in bank financing products for SME's industry.

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